

Preparedness Factors of Bachelor of Elementary Education Graduates for the Licensure Examination for Teachers

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Abstract: This study identifies the factors influencing the preparedness of NEUST Gabaldon Campus BEED graduates before taking the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET). Using a quantitative online survey, data were collected from 18 BEED graduates who took the LET. The research highlights the LET as a key measure of teacher competency and a requirement under RA 7836, emphasizing the academic, emotional, and psychological challenges examinees encounter. Despite NEUST Gabaldon Campus's high LET passing rates -100 % for Secondary and 87.23% for Elementary education first-takers in 2023-the institution faces ongoing challenges in maintaining these outcomes due to diverse factors affecting student preparedness. The study, grounded in the Holistic Teacher Education Institution (TEI) theory, categorizes preparedness factors into personal (study habits, time management, motivation), institutional (review program availability, faculty support), and external (emotional management, social expectations, financial capability, family support). Findings show that attending review sessions, having a positive mindset, self-discipline, and effective time management are crucial for LET's success. The results aim to guide improvements in review programs, mentorship, and support systems, benefiting NEUST and other teacher education institutions in enhancing LET performance and advancing quality education in the Philippines.

Keywords: *Licensure Examination for Teachers, mentorship, LET preparedness, LET performance, review program support, teacher licensure.*

Introduction

The Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET) is an examination that measures the individual ability of aspiring teachers, as required by the Philippine Teachers Professionalization Act (RA 7836). It serves as a key measure of teacher competency, allowing for the evaluation of a future teacher's knowledge, abilities, and skills to ensure they can make valuable contributions to the educational system. The LET is a critical safeguard of educator quality, providing a standard by which to judge whether a graduate has the minimal proficiency required to enter the teaching profession. According to Acosta (2016), the licensure examination has become a significant indicator of educators' quality and the instruction they provide.

The high stakes and importance of passing this examination can lead to diverse emotional, physical, and psychological challenges for examinees. The stigma of failing can be a burden, while successfully passing serves as a rewarding validation of years of hard work. Across the country, LET performance is widely used to measure teacher quality, where low passing rates often reflect institutional challenges related to curriculum effectiveness, resource availability, and student support.

Previous studies highlight the need for systemic improvements in teacher education. Alfonso (2019) indicated that Teacher Education Institutions (TEIs) could improve outcomes by addressing curricular gaps and implementing policy reforms that strengthen mentorship, feedback mechanisms, and LET preparation. Furthermore, research by Antonio et al. (2019) at NEUST found that while graduates had "very satisfactory" academic performance in professional education subjects, their LET scores were notably lower, indicating a need for improved instructional methods to enhance passing rates. The study by Dela Cruz et al. (2022) suggested that while NEUST has produced a considerable number of LET passers, a comparative analysis of passing rates against other institutions in Luzon indicated a need for curricular reforms and enhanced preparatory programs. This highlights the ongoing need for better support mechanisms and resources to sustain and improve LET passing rates.

Despite these universal challenges, the Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology (NEUST) has established a solid reputation, particularly at its Gabaldon Campus, which achieved a remarkable 100% passing rate in 2023 among Secondary first-takers and 87.23% among Elementary first-takers. However, maintaining these high passing rates remains challenging due to complex factors that influence student preparedness. The study by Paler (2024) on LET re-takers' resilience found that this exam presents significant challenges that impact the mental, emotional, and physical well-being of prospective teachers.

This study is grounded in the Holistic Teacher Education Institution (TEI) theory and aims to identify the factors influencing the preparedness of NEUST BEED graduates. The factors are broadly categorized into three areas, each supported by existing literature:

Personal Factors relate to the examinee's individual efforts and skills, such as study habits, time management, and motivation. Effective preparation requires personal accountability, as emphasized by Conley (2005) in *College Knowledge*, which links academic success to cognitive, emotional, and social skills such as time management and goal-setting. Research confirms the critical link between a graduate's academic performance and licensure exam success, underscoring the need for stronger preparation in specialized areas.

Institutional Factors involve the support structures provided by the university, such as the availability of LET review programs and faculty support. Studies consistently show that schools with strong mentorship and comprehensive review processes tend to produce higher passing rates. The correlation between curriculum effectiveness and LET performance suggests that many graduates struggle in major subjects, affecting overall passing rates. Therefore, it is pertinent to connect the aims and methods of pedagogy to the competencies supported in the LET. Furthermore, the role of faculty is also pivotal, as their behaviors, attitudes, and instructional strategies directly affect student performance.

External Factors encompass the outside influences on the examinee, including emotional management, social expectations, financial capability, and family support. The high-stakes nature of the exam presents significant challenges impacting the mental, emotional, and physical well-being of prospective teachers. Moreover, social support is a key predictor of success, as peer support and feedback can boost academic achievement and confidence among re-takers. Family support is particularly important, as expectations from family and professors often motivate students to prepare well.

Methodology

Research Design

This study used a quantitative research design. A quantitative research design is a structured approach that focuses on collecting and analyzing numerical data to identify patterns, relationships, or trends. This approach aimed to quantify the factors influencing students' preparedness for the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET) and determine the relationships between these factors and their preparedness levels.

Understanding these factors provides deep insights into the emotional, physical, and psychological struggles and the positive learning opportunities of incoming takers. By identifying these factors, this study aims to guide university administrators in motivating aspiring teachers, improving teacher education programs, and enhancing examination preparation strategies, ultimately benefiting NEUST and other TEIs in advancing quality education in the Philippines.

Research Locale and Respondents

This study was conducted at the College of Education Department of the Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology (NEUST), Gabaldon Campus. The study aimed to identify the factors influencing the preparedness of the Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEED) graduates who took the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET) in September 2024.

The respondents in the study were LET takers from the College of Education at NEUST, Gabaldon Campus. The research sample comprised eighteen (18) respondents who took the Licensure Examination for Teachers in September 2024. The total population sampling method was utilized, which included the entire population of BEED graduated students from NEUST who took the Licensure examination in September 2024, regardless of their results, including re-takers.

Sample and Sampling Technique

This study was conducted at the College of Education Department of Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology (NEUST), Gabaldon Campus. The research sample comprised eighteen (18) respondents who took the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET) in September 2024.

The sample was selected using the Total Population Sampling method. This non-probability sampling technique was deemed appropriate and employed because the target population—all BEED graduates from NEUST Gabaldon Campus who took the September 2024 LET, including both first-takers and re-takers—was very small, well-defined, and fully accessible.

To ensure that the entire population was identified and covered, the researchers first consulted the University's public publications, such as official lists or announcements, which acknowledged the LET passers. Through coordination with the College of Education, the researchers were able to determine the exact number of BEED graduates who took the examination in September 2024. Given the small, manageable size of this cohort, the researchers made a deliberate effort to reach out to and include every taker in the study. By utilizing the entire population as the sample, this technique eliminates sampling error and allows the findings to be directly and completely reflective of the specific group studied.

Research Instrument

The researchers developed their own research instrument, a structured, close-ended online survey questionnaire titled "Structured Online Survey Guide", to precisely measure the factors influencing the preparedness of BEED graduates. This self-developed instrument was administered via Google Forms to allow the researchers to conveniently reach all chosen respondents regardless of their location and to enable them to answer at their own comfortable pace, which is an appropriate technique for gathering data from a dispersed yet fully included total population sample.

To ensure the instrument's rigor and appropriateness, it underwent a thorough validation process by experts in the field of Education. The validators assessed the instrument for its validity, clarity, comprehensiveness, and cultural appropriateness and provided valuable feedback prior to its final deployment.

Data Collection Procedure

Before collecting the data, researchers sent a formal request form to the office of the Teacher Education Chairperson to ask for access to the list of graduated students of the Teacher Education Program who took the September 2024 Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET), including both first-time and re-takers, as they were the defined respondents for this study. After gaining access to the complete list of respondents, the researchers finalized the online survey questionnaires, which were first checked and approved by their research adviser to ensure alignment with the study objectives. The researchers politely approached the respondents online (via email or social media) to state the purpose of their study and emphasize the importance of their participation.

Researchers ensured that all potential respondents were fully aware that their responses and personal information would be treated with the utmost confidentiality. Only after receiving explicit approval and consent from individuals to participate in the study did the researchers send the Google Form link, which contained questions specifically designed to gather the required information. The researchers then waited for the completed responses to be submitted via the Google Form and then downloaded, cleaned, and analyzed the data for the study.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The collected data were systematically analyzed using quantitative and descriptive statistical approaches. Descriptive statistics, specifically frequency and percentage distributions, were utilized to characterize and present the Socio-Demographic Profile of the respondents. To determine the extent to which various factors affect graduates' LET preparedness, the weighted mean was computed. The interpretation of the weighted mean scores was based on a four-point Likert Scale, which compelled respondents to express a definitive position. The scale's structure for quantifying the level of influence was as follows: a Point of 4, corresponding to a Scale of 3.25–4.00, was interpreted as Strongly Agree; a Point of 3 (Scale of 2.50–3.24) was interpreted as Agree; a Point of 2 (Scale of 1.75–2.49) was interpreted as Disagree; and finally, a Point of 1 (Scale of 1.00–1.74) was interpreted as Strongly Disagree.

Ethics in Research

According to the International Journal of Care Scholars (2018), "When dealing with vulnerable groups of people, qualitative researchers should be aware of potential harm that can be imposed on the participants". These principles ensure that the research is conducted in a respectful, responsible, and trustworthy manner. Before formally beginning data collection, the researcher ensured they provided a clear and understandable explanation of the purpose, any risks (if any), and the benefits of this research, and that they were mindful of protecting participants' rights and of achieving the research objectives. Researchers ensured that participants' personal data were kept confidential.

Results

Profile of the Respondents

Table 1 shows the respondents' ages and sex. Out of 18 LET takers, 4 are age 22 (22.22%), 4 are age 24 (22.22%), and 10 are age 23 (55.56%). Basagre (2020) studied the BEED demographic analysis of graduates at the Central Bicol State University of Agriculture during 2014–2018. Of all BEED graduates, the majority belonged to the 21 to 23 (46.91%) and 24 to 26 (45.68%) age groups, while students aged 27 to 29 accounted for only 7.41%. BEED graduates commonly schedule their LET examination during their undergraduate years, when they are 21 to 23 and 24 to 26 years old, as per the traditional academic schedule in the Philippines. Both age groups, comprising students aged 21 to 23 and 24 to 26, had the highest number of BEED graduates who took the LET examination. The test results of the BEED graduates from the study surpassed those of conventional college-educated age groups. BEED graduates exceeding 21 years old achieved

higher LET test results than young undergraduate students who took the exam before turning 21, according to Delos Angeles (2019). The average LET exam score for BEED graduates aged 21 or older was 75.8 points, while those aged 19 to 20 scored 68.84 points. LET assessments prove more successful for personnel who spend more time preparing and are of an advanced age.

The findings on the age profile of NEUST BEED graduates who took the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET) in September 2024 provide an essential understanding of preparedness. This age range, from 22 to 24 years, accounts for the majority of NEUST BEED graduates who took the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET) in September 2024, as test-takers were distributed equally across these age groups (55.56%), while 23-year-old LET takers accounted for another 55.56% of the test population. Academic support services, along with review programs, have a substantial influence on graduates' preparedness for licensure examinations, according to research. The high number of candidates aged 21 to 24 can affect their exam preparedness, as analyses reveal differing patterns in review material choices, general and professional knowledge retention, study behaviors, and test-taking attitudes among licensure examination test-takers. The demographic profile helps NEUST create more targeted support systems by strengthening review and prevention programs, as recent research shows that mentoring, among other things, improves exam preparedness.

Furthermore, of the 18 LET takers, 2 (11.11%) were male, and 16 (88.89%) were female. Studies confirm that graduate students in the Bachelor of Elementary Education program are mostly female, constituting the main group, while male students remain in the minority. According to Basagre (2020), females outnumber males among BEED graduates to such an extent that males generally make up only about 2 out of every 16 females in selected samples. Educational data demonstrates consistent female domination because women represent the major portion of students pursuing teaching certification. The observed gender imbalance aligns with educational patterns at both the national and international levels. Research by Freeman (2004), together with National Center for Education Statistics (NCES) data, shows that women now outnumber men in both educational enrollment and completion rates over time and therefore lead traditional female-dominated fields like teaching.

The findings regarding to sex of NEUST BEED graduates' LET preparedness produce important implications about their preparedness factors before taking the exam. The examined data show a gender distribution: female participants accounted for 88.89%, while male participants accounted for only 11.11%, reflecting the common gender proportions among elementary education students. Research indicates that LET preparedness depends on college-level preparation activities and on curriculum development integrated with real-world teaching practice, which produce successful outcomes. The examination outcomes of BEED graduates depend on the combination of strong academic preparation and curriculum updates aligned with LET competencies, as targeted assessment programs improve enrollment success rates. Educational stakeholders at NEUST and comparable institutions must establish mentoring systems, retention strategies, and professor development plans to guarantee graduates succeed in the LET and prepare for changing teaching needs.

Table 1

Profile of the Respondents According to Age and Sex.

Age	Frequency	Percentage
22	4	22.22%
23	10	55.56%
24	4	22.22%
Total	18	100%
Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	2	11.11%
Female	16	88.89%
Total	18	100%

Study Habits

Table 2 shows the Study Habits of LET takers. According to the data gathered, respondents strongly agree that everyone prefers to study in a quiet, distraction-free environment, with a weighted mean of 3.72. Likewise, they take regular breaks to avoid burnout during their study sessions, with a computed weighted mean of 3.67. It also showed that respondents strongly agreed they used active recall techniques to retain the information, with a weighted mean of 3.56. Moreover, the respondents organized their study materials well before starting their study sessions, with a weighted mean of 3.5. In addition, the respondents track their progress to stay motivated in their study plans, with a weighted mean of 3.5. Likewise, they utilized online resources and materials to aid their studies, with a weighted mean of 3.44, and the respondents regularly reviewed their lessons to ensure better retention, with a weighted mean of 3.44. Furthermore, they actively participated in group study sessions to enhance their understanding, with a weighted mean of 3.33, and set

regular study time, with a weighted mean of 3.33. The data also showed that the respondents consistently follow their study schedule to prepare for the LET, with a computed weighted mean score of 3.22. Overall, the weighted mean across all statements is 3.47, with a verbal interpretation of strongly agree.

Table 2

Graduates' LET Preparedness Based on Their Study Habits.

Study Habits	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. I set a regular time for studying.	3.33	Strongly Agree
2. I consistently follow my study schedule to prepare for the LET.	3.22	Agree
3. I use active recall techniques to retain information.	3.56	Strongly Agree
4. I take regular breaks to avoid burnout during my study session.	3.67	Strongly Agree
5. I prefer to study in a quiet and distraction-free environment.	3.72	Strongly Agree
6. I regularly review my lessons to ensure better retention.	3.44	Strongly Agree
7. I organize my study materials well before starting my study sessions.	3.5	Strongly Agree
8. I actively participate in group study sessions to enhance my understanding.	3.33	Strongly Agree
9. I utilize online resources and materials to aid my studies.	3.44	Strongly Agree
10. I track my progress to stay motivated in my study plan.	3.5	Strongly Agree
Total weighted Mean	3.47	Strongly Agree

Time Management

Table 3 shows the Time Management of LET takers. According to the data gathered, respondents strongly agreed that good time management is essential for successful LET preparation, with a computed weighted mean of 3.61. Likewise, effectively balanced their study time with other responsibilities, which has a computed weighted mean of 3.61. It also showed that respondents strongly agreed they have a clear plan for managing their time for LET preparation, with a weighted mean of 3.44. Moreover, the respondents were satisfied with the time they used while preparing for the LET, with a weighted mean of 3.44. In addition, the respondents set specific time blocks for different subjects or topics in their study schedule, with a weighted mean of 3.29. Likewise, the respondents reviewed their time management plan regularly to improve it, with a weighted mean of 3.28. The data also showed that the respondents agreed with the time they set for each lesson, with a computed weighted mean of 3.22, and that they avoided spending excessive time on non-essential activities when preparing for the LET, with a weighted mean of 3.22. In Addition, they avoid procrastination and stay on schedule with their study plan (weighted mean of 3.17), and they use a planner or digital calendar to organize their tasks (weighted mean of 3.06). Overall, the weighted mean across all statements is 3.33, with a verbal interpretation of strongly agree.

Table 3

Graduates' LET Preparedness Based on Their Time Management.

Time Management	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. I am satisfied with the time I have used while preparing for the LET.	3.44	Strongly Agree
2. I effectively balance my study time with other responsibilities.	3.61	Strongly Agree
3. I have a clear plan for how to manage my time for LET preparation.	3.44	Strongly Agree
4. I avoid procrastination and stay on schedule with my study plan.	3.17	Agree
5. I make use of a planner or digital calendar to organize my tasks.	3.06	Agree

6. I avoid spending excessive time on non-essential activities when preparing for the LET.	3.22	Agree
7. I set specific time blocks for different subjects or topics in my study schedule.	3.29	Strongly Agree
8. I follow the time I set for each lesson.	3.22	Agree
9. I review my time management plan regularly to improve it.	3.28	Strongly Agree
10. I believe that good time management is essential for successful LET preparation.	3.61	Strongly Agree
Total weighted Mean	3.33	Strongly Agree

Motivation and Goal-Setting

Table 4 shows the Motivation and Goal-Setting of LET takers. According to the data gathered, the respondents strongly agree and strongly desire to become licensed teachers, with a computed weighted mean of 3.83. Likewise, they feel motivated to study because they want to pass the LET, which has a computed weighted mean of 3.61. It also showed that the respondents strongly agreed that they are confident their efforts will help them pass the LET, with a weighted mean of 3.56. Moreover, the respondents remained focused on their goals even in the face of distractions, with a weighted mean of 3.5. In addition, the respondents have clear goals for their LET preparation, with a weighted mean of 3.44. Likewise, the respondents still find it easy to stay motivated during difficult or challenging study sessions (weighted mean of 3.33) and to break down their long-term goals into smaller, achievable tasks (weighted mean of 3.33). The data also showed that the respondents regularly evaluated their progress towards their preparation goals, with a weighted mean score of 3.22, and avoided spending excessive time on non-essential activities when preparing for the LET, with a weighted mean score of 3.22. In Addition, they reward themselves after completing one study session (weighted mean = 3.17) and set daily goals for their LET preparation (computed mean score = 3.11). Overall, the weighted mean for their Motivation and Goal-Setting is 3.41, with a verbal interpretation of strongly agree.

Table 4

Graduates' LET Preparedness Based on Their Motivation and Goal-Setting.

Motivation and Goal-Setting	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. I have clear goals set for my LET preparation.	3.44	Strongly Agree
2. I regularly evaluate my progress towards my preparation goals.	3.22	Agree
3. I feel motivated to study because I want to pass the LET.	3.61	Strongly Agree
4. I break down my long-term goals into smaller, achievable tasks.	3.33	Strongly Agree
5. I reward myself after completing one study session.	3.17	Agree
6. I have a strong desire to become a licensed teacher.	3.83	Strongly Agree
7. I still find it easy to stay motivated during difficult or challenging study sessions.	3.33	Strongly Agree
8. I set daily goals for my LET preparation.	3.11	Agree
9. I stay focused on my goals, even when faced with distractions.	3.50	Strongly Agree
10. I am confident that my efforts will help me pass the LET.	3.56	Strongly Agree
Total weighted Mean	3.41	Strongly Agree

Availability of LET Review Programs

Table 5 shows the availability of LET review programs for LET takers. The respondents strongly agree that the review programs are essential for LET success, with a weighted mean of 3.78, and that these programs contributed positively to their preparation, with a computed weighted mean of 3.61. It also showed that the university contributed to their preparation, as they strongly agree that NEUST offers review materials that are relevant to the LET content, with a weighted mean of 3.56. Moreover, the respondents stated that the NEUST suggested review programs were well-

structured and comprehensive and could help prepare for the LET, with a weighted mean of 3.5. In addition, they indicate that the review programs include mock exams that simulate the actual LET, with a weighted mean of 3.39. Likewise, they believe the duration of the LET review programs is adequate to cover all essential topics, and they are given a chance to participate in any review program and review centers, with a weighted mean of 3.33. They also use the learning resources from my university for their LET preparation, which has a weighted mean of 3.33. The schedule of the review programs also fits with their personal availability, with a weighted mean of 3.28. The review programs provide personalized feedback to improve their performance, with a computed weighted mean score of 3.22. The overall weighted mean was 3.43, indicating strong agreement that review programs are beneficial.

Table 5*Availability of LET Review Programs.*

Availability of LET review programs	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. The duration of the LET review programs is adequate to cover all essential topics.	3.33	Strongly Agree
2. The NEUST suggested review programs that are well-structured and comprehensive and could help in preparation for LET.	3.5	Strongly Agree
3. I participated in review programs and review centers.	3.33	Strongly Agree
4. The review programs have contributed positively to my LET preparation.	3.61	Strongly Agree
5. The schedule of the review programs fits my personal availability.	3.28	Strongly Agree
6. NEUST offers review materials that are relevant to the LET content.	3.56	Strongly Agree
7. I have used the learning resources from my university for my preparation for the LET.	3.33	Strongly Agree
8. The review programs include mock exams that help simulate the actual LET.	3.39	Strongly Agree
9. The review programs provide personalized feedback to improve my performance.	3.22	Agree
10. I believe that the review programs are essential for LET's success.	3.78	Strongly Agree
Total weighted Mean	3.43	Strongly Agree

Faculty and Support Guidance

Table 6 shows the faculty support and guidance for the LET takers. The data show that the respondents trust the expertise of their professors in guiding them on LET preparation with a weighted mean of 3.44, they also feel that their professors are invested in helping them pass the LET with a weighted mean of 3.5, with connection with that they are satisfied with the support and guidance provided by faculty in preparing students for the LET which has a weighted mean of 3.5. They strongly agreed that the faculty provides valuable resources that assist in their LET preparation, and their professors encourage them to stay focused and motivated for the LET, with both having a weighted mean of 3.33. The respondents strongly agree that the faculty of NEUST provides useful guidance for LET preparation, and they also receive feedback on their academic work from faculty, which helps them stay motivated while preparing for the LET. This shows that the faculty members are responsive to student inquiries related to LET preparation, with all having a weighted mean of 3.28. They find that regularly seeking advice from professors about LET preparation could also help them, as they know that Professors at NEUST are available to answer questions related to LET preparation, with both having a weighted mean of 3.22. The overall weighted mean was 3.34, showing strong agreement with the positive impact of faculty support.

Table 6*Faculty and Support Guidance.*

Faculty and Support Guidance	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. The faculty at NEUST provides useful guidance for LET preparation.	3.28	Strongly Agree

2. I regularly seek advice from my professors about LET preparation.	3.22	Agree
3. Professors at NEUST are available to answer questions related to LET preparation.	3.22	Agree
4. The feedback I receive from faculty on my academic work helps me prepare for the LET.	3.28	Strongly Agree
5. I feel that my professors are invested in helping me pass the LET.	3.5	Strongly Agree
6. The faculty provides valuable resources that assist in my LET preparation.	3.33	Strongly Agree
7. My professors encourage me to stay focused and motivated for the LET.	3.33	Strongly Agree
8. I am satisfied with the support and guidance provided by the faculty in preparing students for the LET.	3.5	Strongly Agree
9. Faculty members are responsive to student inquiries related to LET preparation.	3.28	Strongly Agree
10. I trust the expertise of my professors in guiding my LET preparation.	3.44	Strongly Agree
Total weighted Mean	3.34	Strongly Agree

Graduates' Emotional Management Strategies

Table 7 shows the emotional management strategies of the LET takers. Respondents used positive affirmations to boost their emotional resilience (weighted mean of 3.56) and sought support from friends or family when they felt overwhelmed by LET preparation (weighted mean of 3.5). They also agree that it is helpful to talk about their emotional concerns related to LET preparation, which has a weighted mean of 3.5. They believe that emotional management is an important part of their LET preparation (3.39) so that they avoid negative thoughts when facing difficulties in their studies, which also has a weighted mean of 3.19. LET takers maintain a positive attitude during their LET preparation (weighted mean of 3.33) and actively manage stress (weighted mean of 3.17). Taking time for self-care helps them feel emotionally ready for the LET, with a weighted mean of 3.28. It includes maintaining emotional balance, even when faced with setbacks in their preparation, which has a weighted mean of 3.28. Practicing relaxation techniques, such as deep breathing, is one of their emotional strategies to reduce anxiety (3.22). The overall weighted mean was 3.36, with respondents strongly agreeing that emotional management is important.

Table 7

Graduates' Emotional Management Strategies.

Emotional Management Strategies	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. I actively manage stress during my LET preparation.	3.17	Agree
2. I practice relaxation techniques, such as deep breathing, to reduce anxiety.	3.22	Agree
3. I am able to maintain a positive attitude during my LET preparation.	3.33	Strongly Agree
4. I seek support from friends or family when I feel overwhelmed by LET preparation.	3.5	Strongly Agree
5. I avoid negative thoughts when facing difficulties in my studies.	3.39	Strongly Agree
6. I take time for self-care to ensure I am emotionally ready for the LET.	3.28	Strongly Agree
7. I maintain emotional balance, even when faced with setbacks in my preparation.	3.28	Strongly Agree
8. I find it helpful to talk about my emotional concerns related to LET preparation.	3.5	Strongly Agree
9. I use positive affirmations to boost my emotional resilience.	3.56	Strongly Agree

10. Emotional management is an important part of my LET preparation.	3.39	Strongly Agree
Total weighted Mean	3.36	Strongly Agree

Social Expectations

Table 8 shows the social Expectations for the LET takers. Respondents believe that family support is important in meeting social expectations related to the LET, with a weighted mean of 3.6, while they try to manage these expectations while focusing on their own goals for the LET, with a weighted mean of 3.44. They also strongly agree that their professors' expectations motivate them to prepare well for the LET, with a weighted mean of 3.44. This data also showed that social expectations positively influence preparation for the LET with a weighted mean of 3.33. LET takers didn't feel overwhelmed by the pressure of meeting others' expectations, as it has a weighted mean of 3.22, and they are confident that they can meet the expectations placed on them for the LET with a weighted mean of 3.22 and they don't feel pressure from their family to perform well on the LET, which has a weighted mean of 3.22. This also indicates that their society as well didn't make them pressure for having high expectations for them to pass the exam which has a weighted mean of 2.94 and they are motivated to pass the LET because of the expectations from their peers which has a weighted mean of 2.94 and lastly, they didn't experience stress due to the expectations placed on them by others regarding the LET which has a weighted mean of 2.72. The overall weighted mean was 3.21, indicating a verbal interpretation of the agreement.

Table 8

Social Expectations.

Social Expectations	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. I don't feel pressure from my family to perform well on the LET.	3.22	Agree
2. My society didn't put pressure on me to have high expectations for me to pass the LET.	2.94	Agree
3. I didn't experience stress due to the expectations placed on me by others regarding the LET.	2.72	Agree
4. I am motivated to pass the LET because of the expectations from my peers.	2.94	Agree
5. I believe that social expectations positively influence my preparation for the LET.	3.33	Strongly Agree
6. I didn't feel overwhelmed by the pressure of meeting others' expectations.	3.22	Agree
7. I try to manage social expectations while focusing on my own goals for the LET.	3.44	Strongly Agree
8. The expectations of my professors motivate me to prepare well for the LET.	3.44	Strongly Agree
9. I believe that family support is important in meeting social expectations related to the LET.	3.61	Strongly Agree
10. I am confident that I can meet the expectations placed on me for the LET.	3.22	Agree
Total weighted Mean	3.21	Agree

Financial Capability

Table 9 shows the financial capability of the LET takers. Respondents budget their finances to ensure they can cover the costs related to the LET with a weighted mean of 3.39 because they believe that financial support is essential to their overall preparedness for the LET, which has a weighted mean of 3.56, and they have received financial assistance from family or others to support their LET preparation, which has a weighted mean of 3.5. It was shown that they are satisfied with the current financial resources available for their LET preparation (weighted mean of 3.33) and confident they can afford the LET examination fees (weighted mean of 3.28). It was clear that while preparing for the exam they have the financial resources to enroll in LET review programs, which has a weighted mean of 3.11. Majority of LET takers agree that financial challenges do not significantly hinder their LET preparation and they are not worried about not having enough money for the LET preparation which both are has a weighted mean of 3.06. This data shows that LET takers can

access additional funding sources for LET-related expenses (weighted mean of 3) and are allotted financial means to purchase necessary study materials for the LET (weighted mean of 2.83). The overall weighted mean was 3.21, with respondents generally agreeing that financial capability influences preparedness.

Table 9*Financial Capabilities of Graduates to Take the LET.*

Financial Capability	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. I have the financial resources to enroll in LET review programs.	3.11	Agree
2. I am confident that I can afford the fees for the LET examination.	3.28	Strongly Agree
3. Financial challenges do not significantly hinder my LET preparation.	3.06	Agree
4. I have the financial means to purchase the necessary study materials for the LET.	2.83	Agree
5. I didn't worry about not having enough money for the LET preparation.	3.06	Agree
6. I have received financial assistance from family or others to support my LET preparation.	3.5	Strongly Agree
7. I budget my finances to ensure I can cover the costs related to the LET.	3.39	Strongly Agree
8. I can access additional funding sources if needed for LET-related expenses.	3	Agree
9. I am satisfied with the current financial resources available for my LET preparation.	3.33	Strongly Agree
10. Financial support is essential to my overall preparedness for the LET.	3.56	Strongly Agree
Total weighted Mean	3.21	Agree

Family Support

Table 10 shows the family support for LET takers. This data showed that LET takers feel their families believe in their ability to pass the LET. With a weighted mean of 3.72, they receive emotional support from their family during their LET preparation, which has a weighted mean of 3.67. Moreover, they are able to balance their family responsibilities with their preparation for the LET, with a weighted mean of 3.67. Respondents' reports being more motivated to study for the LET because of their family's support, and Family support plays a crucial role in their confidence to take the LET, with both having a weighted mean of 3.61. They strongly agree that their family has been actively involved in their LET preparation process (weighted mean of 3.61) and that it has provided sufficient financial support for their LET preparation (weighted mean of 3.56). According to the data gathered, LET takers rely on their families for guidance when faced with challenges during LET preparation (weighted mean of 3.56), and their families encourage them to study hard for the LET (weighted mean of 3.44). This also indicates that their family helps them manage their time for study sessions with a weighted mean of 3.39. The overall weighted mean was 3.58, the highest among all factors, indicating strong agreement on the crucial role of family support.

Table 10*Family Support for Graduates Taking the LET.*

Family Support	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. My family encourages me to study hard for the LET.	3.44	Strongly Agree
2. I receive emotional support from my family during my LET preparation.	3.67	Strongly Agree
3. My family helps me manage my time for study sessions.	3.39	Strongly Agree
4. My family has provided enough financial support for my LET preparation.	3.56	Strongly Agree

5. I feel that my family believes in my ability to pass the LET.	3.72	Strongly Agree
6. I am motivated to study for the LET because of my family's support.	3.61	Strongly Agree
7. I can rely on my family for guidance when faced with challenges during LET preparation.	3.56	Strongly Agree
8. Family support plays a crucial role in my confidence to take the LET.	3.61	Strongly Agree
9. I am able to balance my family responsibilities with my LET preparation.	3.67	Strongly Agree
10. My family has been actively involved in my LET preparation process.	3.61	Strongly Agree
Total weighted Mean	3.58	Strongly Agree

Discussion

The respondents of this study were eighteen (18) Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEED) graduates from Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology (NEUST), Gabaldon Campus, who took the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET) in September 2024. Most of the respondents were female, single, and aged 22 to 24. This demographic profile aligns with national and institutional trends showing higher female participation in elementary education programs and reflects the typical age at which graduates attempt professional licensure examinations in the Philippines. Establishing this profile provides important context for understanding the preparedness factors influencing LET performance.

The findings reveal that personal factors, particularly study habits, time management, motivation, and goal-setting, play a vital role in the preparedness of BEED graduates for the LET. Respondents demonstrated strong study habits, including studying in quiet and distraction-free environments, using active recall techniques, organizing study materials, and taking regular breaks to avoid burnout. These practices support effective learning and information retention, which are essential for high-stakes examinations such as the LET (Abdulrahman et al., 2021). Time management also emerged as a significant contributor to preparedness. The respondents reported effectively balancing study time with other responsibilities, setting time blocks for different subjects, and recognizing the importance of proper scheduling in their LET preparation. These findings suggest that disciplined time allocation enables examinees to manage the extensive coverage of LET content more efficiently (Sanico & Espinosa, 2025).

Motivation and goal-setting further strengthened LET preparedness. The respondents expressed a strong desire to become licensed teachers, clear academic goals, confidence in their efforts, and the ability to stay motivated even during challenging review sessions. These results indicate that intrinsic motivation and well-defined goals help sustain persistence and focus throughout the preparation period, reinforcing readiness for the examination (Eckerlein et al., 2019).

Institutional support was found to be a crucial factor influencing LET preparedness, particularly through the availability of LET review programs and faculty guidance. Respondents strongly agreed that NEUST's review programs were essential in helping them prepare for the LET. The structured nature of the review sessions, the inclusion of mock examinations, the relevance of the review materials, and their alignment with LET content contributed positively to their readiness.

Faculty support and guidance were also highly valued by the respondents. The availability of professors to answer questions, provide feedback, offer encouragement, and share relevant resources enhanced both academic and emotional preparedness. These findings underscore the importance of strong mentorship, responsive faculty involvement, and well-designed institutional programs in improving licensure examination readiness among teacher education graduates (Abao et al., 2023).

External factors—including emotional management strategies, social expectations, financial capability, and family support—also played a significant role in shaping LET preparedness. Respondents employed various emotional coping strategies such as positive affirmations, relaxation techniques, and seeking emotional support from family and peers to manage stress and anxiety associated with LET preparation. This highlights the importance of emotional resilience in sustaining confidence and focus during exam preparation.

Social expectations were found to have both motivational and supportive influences. While respondents generally did not feel overwhelmed by societal pressure, encouragement from family, peers, and professors positively motivated them to prepare for the LET. Financial capability was also identified as a contributing factor, as adequate financial resources enabled respondents to enroll in review programs, purchase study materials, and cover examination-related expenses.

Financial assistance from family played a key role in minimizing financial stress and allowing respondents to focus on their preparation (Stevenson et al., 2021)

Among all external factors, family support emerged as the strongest influence on LET preparedness. Respondents consistently reported receiving emotional encouragement, financial assistance, time management support, and reassurance from their families, which built their confidence. This strong familial involvement enhanced motivation, reduced anxiety, and strengthened the respondents' overall readiness to take the LET (Panlaqui, 2025).

Overall, the findings demonstrate that LET preparedness among BEED graduates is shaped by an interconnected set of personal, institutional, and external factors. Effective study habits, strong time management, and high motivation form the personal foundation for readiness. These are reinforced by institutional mechanisms such as review programs and faculty mentorship, while external supports—especially emotional regulation and family assistance—provide stability and confidence. The integration of these factors highlights the need for a holistic approach to teacher education and LET preparation.

Conclusion

The demographic findings of this study indicate that the majority of LET takers were female, single, and within the 22-24 age range, a profile consistent with the typically higher female enrollment in elementary education programs and the standard age for recent graduates entering the teaching profession in the Philippines. This finding provides essential context for interpreting the study's findings and for tailoring relevant support and interventions to enhance LET preparedness and success for this specific group of aspiring educators.

This study concludes that BEED graduates' preparedness for the LET is influenced by a combination of personal, institutional, and external factors. Personal factors play a significant role, encompassing a student's study habits, time management skills, motivation, and goal-setting. Effective study habits, such as studying in a distraction-free environment, taking regular breaks, and utilizing active recall techniques, are crucial for retaining information. Similarly, strong time-management skills enable LET takers to balance their study schedules with other responsibilities, ensuring comprehensive preparation. A high level of motivation and clearly defined goals further drive students to stay focused and persistent throughout their review process, even in the face of distractions. These personal attributes collectively contribute to a student's ability to approach the LET with confidence and a structured plan. Institutional support from teacher education institutions (TEIs) also significantly influences LET preparedness.

Well-structured, comprehensive LET review programs that include mock exams and personalized feedback can greatly enhance a student's understanding of the exam format and content. Faculty support and guidance, characterized by mentorship and relevant review materials, provide aspiring teachers with the necessary academic and emotional scaffolding. TEIs that offer robust review programs and foster a supportive learning environment tend to produce graduates who are better equipped to handle the demands of the LET. This highlights the importance of institutional commitment to ensuring student success in licensure examinations.

Beyond personal and institutional factors, external factors can also impact LET preparedness. Emotional management strategies, such as mindfulness and relaxation exercises, are essential for coping with the stress and anxiety associated with high-stakes examinations. Social expectations from family, peers, and society can add pressure, affecting a test-taker's confidence and overall preparedness. Financial capability plays a crucial role, as it determines a student's ability to afford review programs, study materials, and examination fees. Finally, strong family support, including emotional encouragement and practical assistance, can provide a stable foundation as students navigate the challenges of LET preparation. This study emphasizes the importance of a holistic approach to teacher education that addresses these various personal, institutional, and external factors and their sub-variables to better prepare future educators for the LET and their professional careers.

A combination of effective study routines and robust coping strategies is crucial for improving BEED graduates' preparedness for the LET. In terms of study habits, this study shows that BEED graduates strongly agree that studying in a quiet and distraction-free environment, taking regular breaks, and using active recall techniques are highly beneficial. Organizing study materials, utilizing online resources, and tracking study progress also contribute significantly to their preparedness. Furthermore, the respondents emphasize the importance of consistent review, participation in group study sessions, and adhering to a regular study schedule. These routines, collectively, foster a focused, structured approach to LET preparation, enabling BEED graduates to manage their time effectively and deepen their understanding of the subject matter.

Beyond academic preparation, it highlights the importance of emotional and psychological well-being. BEED graduates recognized the need for effective coping mechanisms to manage the stress and anxiety associated with the LET. The findings reveal that maintaining a positive attitude, seeking social support, and practicing self-care are essential

strategies. Additionally, graduates find it helpful to talk about their emotional concerns, use positive affirmations, and actively manage stress through relaxation techniques. This comprehensive approach, which integrates sound study habits with proactive stress management, can equip BEED graduates with the resilience and confidence needed to excel in the Licensure Examination for Teachers.

Recommendations

Teacher Education Institutions are encouraged to continuously strengthen their support systems, particularly in enhancing LET review programs and faculty support, to ensure that graduates are well-prepared for the Licensure Examination. Faculty members may be encouraged to provide consistent, relevant guidance and learning resources, with an emphasis on improving students' study habits, time management skills, and motivation. In this regard, NEUST Gabaldon Campus may adopt a holistic approach to student development by addressing not only academic preparation but also personal and external factors that influence LET readiness. Integrating time management strategies into the Teacher Education Curriculum and establishing mentorship programs that pair students with faculty for personalized guidance can further support students' preparation. Moreover, Teacher Education Institutions may conduct awareness campaigns to educate families and communities about the pressures students face in preparing for high-stakes examinations, thereby strengthening external support systems. Institutions may also prioritize the development of personal factors by embedding structured study routines, motivational strategies, and self-regulation skills into academic programs to enhance LET preparedness and future teaching effectiveness. In addition, providing financial aid or scholarship programs, access to free or low-cost review materials, and forming partnerships with external organizations or sponsors may help alleviate financial barriers related to LET preparation. Finally, future researchers may consider conducting qualitative studies to explore in greater depth the influence of emotional management, social expectations, financial capability, and family support on LET preparedness, thereby contributing to the development of more comprehensive and responsive support strategies.

Conflict of Interest Statement

The authors declare that there are no financial, personal, institutional, or professional conflicts of interest that could have influenced the conduct, analysis, or reporting of this research. The study was carried out independently and objectively, and all results are presented honestly and transparently.

AI Use Declaration

This study utilized artificial intelligence (AI)-assisted tools solely for language refinement, grammar checking, and clarity improvement during the manuscript preparation process. The AI tools were not used to generate research data, analyze results, interpret findings, or draw conclusions. All research design decisions, data collection, analysis, and interpretations remain the full responsibility of the authors

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